

Structural development on Ru and RuO₂ electrodes during oxygen evolution – a soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy approach

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ABSTRACT

Time resolved *in-situ* X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) in soft X-ray region was used to characterize polarized interphase on Ru and Ru oxide based electrodes under oxygen evolution reaction (OER) conditions. XAS spectra were used to align the type and population of oxygen-containing species formed at electrodes at anodic potentials with local electronic structure of the OER catalyst. The soft XAS data do not identify a single rate limiting process for OER at potentials negative to 1.7 V vs. RHE. Individual intermediates of the oxygen evolution process coexist at the surface at potentials preceding the actual OER onset. The OER is accompanied with redistribution of the electron density resulting for a start of the catalytic cycle reflecting the transfer of the electrons from water to the external circuit during catalyzed water oxidation. The observed spectral behavior indicates a confinement of the OER to the coordination unsaturated sites (*cus*) at the surface.

1. Introduction

Electrocatalytic processes relevant to water electrolysis have become one of the most studied electrochemical systems in the last decade. The interest in these processes has been triggered mainly by its societal relevance, since the water electrolysis is the primary candidate for needed renewable energy storage to replace fossil fuels [1]. A technological application of water electrolysis for industrial hydrogen production has been known for more than a century, its application to mitigate the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources, however, still presents a major technological challenge [2-4]. Development of water electrolysis systems is focused mainly on application exploring acid media [3], or alkaline media [5]. Regardless of the technological differences specific to individual electrolyzer type, the efficiency of water electrolysis is ultimately restricted by activity and stability of the catalytically active phases supporting the electrode reactions (hydrogen and oxygen evolution at the cathode and anode, respectively). Kinetically sluggish oxygen evolution reaction (OER) is deemed to be the limiting process for the overall efficiency, while the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) at the cathode can be optimized and scaled up with less difficulty [6].

The need to develop novel, advanced, highly active anodes for

oxygen evolution fueled vigorous research aimed at the fundamentals of the oxygen evolution process. The alkaline water electrolysis, employing for OER transition metal oxides based on, e.g., Mn, Ni, Fe, or Co [7-10], is considered as a mature water electrolysis technology. The efficiency and flexibility of the polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) cells operating in acidic media [4,11], on the other hand, makes these systems highly attractive for further optimization. The applicability of PEM water electrolyzers is restricted by limited supply of stable and feasible OER catalysts which are so far based on Ru and Ir [12-14]. The scarcity of these materials, namely that of Ir, hinders the projected scale of the hydrogen production. The limited supply of the catalytic materials for oxygen evolution in acid media can be mitigated either by a development of novel systems [15] or by optimization of the Ir and Ru catalytic surfaces allowing to minimize the surface loading while maintaining the activity. It ought to be noted that this approach needs to be backed up by detailed understanding of the oxygen evolution mechanism on atomic level. Unfortunately, the actual mechanism of the oxygen evolving process, despite the attention paid to the topic, remains a subject of debate [13].

In addition to its practical significance, the OER may serve as a model system for (electro)catalytic processes, where the reaction sequence assumes the formation of intermediates with different binding order to

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the surface. Generally accepted theoretical approach to OER optimization represents a practical application of the Brønsted-Polanyi relations [16], and operates with a concept when the overall reaction proceeds as a sequence of four elementary reaction steps:

where S depicts an active site at the surface.

It needs to be noted that this model assumes a formation of three distinctive intermediates confined to the catalyst's surface, $S-OH$, $S-O$ and $S-OOH$. The model identifies the structure of the prospective intermediates as the most stable of the theoretically conceived moieties. Unfortunately, the identity of the reaction intermediates relies solely on theoretical models and their presence (and abundance) still needs to be experimentally proved. The traditional approach [16] assumes that all reaction steps are confined to the same surface moiety. An alternative model assuming a bifunctional proton transfer at the surface has been proposed and elaborated in the past decade [17-19], though its applicability has never been experimentally verified.

A general feature of the computational models supporting rational prediction of catalyst activity trends is their reliance on the reaction mechanisms inherently embedded in the computational model. In addition, the underlying theoretical concept – the Brønsted-Polanyi relations – is in fact thermodynamic in nature, and has, in principle, limitations to identify the rate limiting step of the overall electrode process.

These fundamental drawbacks limit the power of the rational design approach towards tailored catalytic surfaces and one has to admit that the actual active site determination, as well as determination of the rate limiting step(s), is difficult to address experimentally. Traditional spectro-electrochemical techniques originally developed for characterization of metal electrodes utilizing X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) [20] in hard X-ray range turned out to be less convenient for OER investigations given the limited surface sensitivity on most oxide catalysts featuring characteristic particle size bigger than 10 nm.

These experimental obstacles could be avoided if one concentrates on the process-triggered changes in the populations of oxygen in the anionic sublattice as well as in the interphase. Monitoring the behavior of oxygen in the system through spectroscopy may locate the active site (s) as well as identify the accumulation of reaction intermediates at the electrode surface in dependence on the electrode potential. Two types of *in-situ/operando* soft-X-ray spectroscopies have been introduced recently, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy [21-22] and soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy [23-28]. Both approaches have been applied to rationalize the behavior of IrO_x based systems. These techniques have been used less frequently to address the behavior of catalysts based on oxides of Ru [29], which are more abundant and more active but less stable than those of Ir.

This paper describes the behavior of two Ru based electrocatalytic systems in the acidic oxygen evolution as assessed by real-time observation of oxygen evolution by wavelength-dispersive XAS namely focusing on O K-edge reflecting the local electronic structure around Ru.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Real-time XAS experiment

Real-time XAS measurements on O K-edge during oxygen evolution were performed in total fluorescence-yield mode using wavelength-dispersive XAS approach [25]. All the experiments were performed at

the beamline BL-16A of the Photon Factory of the High Energy Accelerator Research Organization (KEK), Japan [26]. Fig. 1 shows the schematic image of the apparatus configuration. The electrochemical cell filled with liquid electrolyte solution (0.1 M $HClO_4$) was separated from the high vacuum part of the XAS apparatus (beamline and imaging optics) by a Si_3N_4 window (NTT-AT Japan), which was fabricated on a Si wafer with a thickness of 200 nm and dimensions of 1 mm \times 3 mm.

The spatial dispersion of the synchrotron radiation at exit slit of the soft X-ray monochromator [24] was achieved with a 500-lines/mm diffraction grating optimized to provide soft X-rays around the O K-edge (approximately 530 eV). Incoming X-rays on the grating are diffracted according to their wavelength at distinctive angles and as a result of it, individual wavelengths hit different positions at the sample. The fluorescence signals proportional to the absorption of incident soft X-rays were recorded simultaneously using metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) camera (Marana-X, Andor) used as a detector (pixel size and detection area were 6.5 $\mu m \times 6.5 \mu m$ and 13 mm \times 13 mm, respectively). The spatial separation of the fluorescence X-ray signals was ensured by two spherical mirrors (see Fig. 1). The intensity readings from each pixel of the CMOS camera were converted into absorption coefficient at individual energy. To compensate for energy dependence of incident X-ray intensity and position dependence of the detection efficiency, the measured fluorescence signals were normalized by those of CaF_2 representing I_0 . Details of this arrangement are given in references [25,27]. The combination of the optical setup and window size allows to collect O K-edge spectra simultaneously over a range of 10 eV which was set to 525–535 eV interval to avoid excessive fluorescence from the bulk water. The time-resolution was of ca. 3 s per spectrum.

2.2. Electrochemical cell set-up

The electrochemical part of the experiments was realized in a three electrode PTFE single compartment cell with Pt auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode [28]. All potentials were then recalculated and are quoted in RHE scale. The PTFE cell was equipped with a Si_3N_4 window (see above) to provide a connection to high-vacuum part of the beamline. The working electrodes composed of Ru or RuO_2 were deposited directly on Si_3N_4 window. Both types of electrodes were initially prepared by Ru deposition by electron beam evaporation (E-flux, ADCAP Vacuum Technology Co., Ltd.). The thickness of the deposited Ru was 20 nm (with 10 nm of sputtered Ti underlayer on Si_3N_4 window before depositing Ru). RuO_2 electrode was prepared by a thermal oxidation of deposited Ru layer in air at 600 °C for 1 hour. The thickness of the deposited layers and underlayers was optimized to achieve <60 % of the attenuation of the X-rays in the electrode and interphase to enable a detection of the generated fluorescence from the backside through the window. It needs to be noted that the actual surface composition of the thermally grown oxide electrode bears an uncertainty given by the possible diffusion of Ti from the underlayer to the top of the electrode upon annealing. A possible presence of the Ti in the active layer of the electrode, however, does not decrease the relevance of the prepared electrodes as it mimics the composition of the industry grade dimension stable anodes (DSA) [30].

The deposited electrodes were contacted by an indium solder. The solder and contacting lead were insulated by non-conductive epoxy resin. The potential control during the experiments was realized by an HSV-110 automatic polarization system (Hokuto Denko, Japan). All experiments were performed in 0.1 M $HClO_4$ (pH=1) which was de-aerated prior and during experiments. The spectro-electrochemical characterization of both types of OER active electrodes was based on cyclic polarization at polarization rate of 5 mV/s. The applied potential perturbation protocol in contrast to more conventional XAS studies attains a time resolution that can better distinguish between reversible and irreversible processes accompanying the oxygen evolution. The attained time resolution is supported by the specific characteristics of the beamline setup and needs to be also supported by a high lateral chemical

Fig. 1. Schematic image of the apparatus of the wavelength-dispersive XAS and dedicated electrochemical cell for the measurement. XAS spectra of O K-edge for the Ru or RuO₂ electrode are obtained in real time.

homogeneity of the prepared electrodes.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electrochemical behavior

The electrocatalytic activity relevant to oxygen evolution of both Ru and RuO₂ is reflected in cyclic voltammograms presented in Fig. 2. These voltammograms were recorded simultaneously with acquisition of wavelength dispersive X-ray absorption spectra on O K-edge. As expected, both vapor-deposited Ru and thermally grown RuO₂ are active in oxygen evolution in acid media. As seen at the Figs. 2(a) and (b), the electrochemical activity of sputtered Ru is significantly higher than that of thermally grown RuO₂. In the case of Ru electrode, the anodic polarization in acid media triggers a formation of a surface oxide which is reflected in a gradual increase of the anodic current at electrode potentials positive to ca. 1.1 V vs. RHE. Further polarization eventually leads to the evolution of gaseous oxygen at potentials positive to ca. 1.48 V vs. RHE as shown by the observed exponential increase in anodic current. It also needs to be noted that the observed anodic activity of Ru electrodes decreases with repetitive cycling, suggesting limited stability of Ru electrode at anodic potentials as reported previously [28]. It ought to be stressed that the potential of the exponential anodic current increase differs slightly from the potential reported in the literature [31]. These differences can be attributed to the uncompensated resistance connected with a thin layer character of the electrode (see below). Despite this deviation from the literature data the onset of the exponential anodic current increase still serves as qualitative marker distinguishing potential region where an expectation of a formation of gaseous oxygen is reasonable.

The activity of the thermally grown RuO₂ is much lower than that of the Ru electrodes (see Fig. 2(b)). In contrast to Ru electrodes, no formation of surface oxide can be tracked in the voltammogram. The onset of the anodic current increase attributable to oxygen evolution appears at significantly more positive potentials than in the case of the Ru electrodes. Lower activity of thermally grown RuO₂ is in part compensated by increased stability in repetitive cycling.

The voltametric behavior of both Ru as well as RuO₂ electrodes is also characterized by a small double layer charge, as shown by the small to negligible hysteresis between anodic and cathodic branches of the voltammograms in the double layer region (see Fig. 2(a) and (b)). More

pronounced hysteresis between anodic and cathodic branches of the voltammogram of RuO₂ electrode attests to higher double-layer capacitance. In both cases, however, the capacitive current gets dominated by uncompensated iR due to inherently high resistance of the thin layer arrangement which drives the current in both anodic and cathodic branches to anodic values. Low double layer capacitance, unfortunately, does not allow to distinguish any changes in the formation as well dissolution of the surface oxides preceding the oxygen evolution reaction.

3.2. Real-time XAS spectroscopy

Typical real-time XAS data recorded during cyclic polarization of the RuO₂ based electrode to potentials relevant to oxygen evolution in acid media are shown in Fig. 3. The fact that O K-edge X-ray absorption spectra were collected in energy-dispersive mode allows to attain rather high time resolution to follow chemical changes in the interphase on the second- timescale [25]. As a result, each plotted spectrum represents a state of the electrode and interphase at a different potential. The potential difference between two consecutive spectra corresponds to ca 15 mV.

As can be seen from the geometry of the experiment described in reference [23,24] X-ray absorption spectra integrate the information of all oxygen atoms present in the electrode, interphase or in the solution which are exposed to the X-ray excitation beam. The spectra presented in Fig. 3 show two main regions of apparently increased absorption located roughly between 530 and 532 eV and then above 533 eV. The absorption in the first region reflects the population of oxygen atoms confined to the catalyst either in its bulk (the studied catalysts are of oxide nature at OER conditions) [32] or as OER intermediates (OH, O and OOH) [29]. It also contains absorption of gaseous oxygen formation of which needs to be taken into account namely at positive potentials. The characteristic absorption of molecular oxygen has been reported at 531 eV [33] which, unfortunately, coincides with the characteristic absorption of surface confined OOH [29]. The second region of the increased absorption (above 533 eV) corresponds generally to absorption of water confined oxygen [34].

A deconvolution of the experimental spectra into its individual components would seem an ideal way of analyzing the spectra presented in Fig. 3. Such process is, however, rather difficult. There are two principal complications one faces in the process. First of all, one needs to

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms recorded on (a) vapor-deposited Ru and (b) thermally grown RuO₂ electrode in 0.1 M HClO₄ at polarization rate of 5 mV/s.

reconcile the fact that the O K-edge spectra of some of the contributing species (oxygen, water, bulk Ru oxides) are known and experimentally accessible. The information on the absorption of the OER intermediates is accessible only by computation [29] and cannot be verified experimentally.

The second complication in the deconvolution of the experimental spectra rests with the fact that the O K-edge absorption in the accessible spectral range (525–535 eV) does not represent an excitation of the 1 s electron of oxygen into continuum (which would yield a single transition) but into antibonding 2p* orbitals. This may complicate significantly the interpretation of the spectra if the absorbing oxygen atoms are confined to a solid (bulk oxygen of the ruthenium oxide(s), OER intermediates). In such a case one may excite 1 s electron of solid confined oxygen into several energy states. In the particular case of Ru oxides one may expect two absorption signals reflecting the excitation of the oxygen's 1 s electron into bands formed by hybridization of 2p* antibonding orbitals with Ru 3d t_{2g} or Ru 3d e_g orbitals. It means that each oxygen bound to Ru oxide should give two absorption signals which ought to be separated by 2.6 eV [32]. As a result, a change of absorbance observed experimentally does not need to represent a change in the population of

the absorbing atoms but may be also significantly affected by the local electronic structure, which affects availability of final states for the 1 s electron excitation.

To avoid most of these complications one may employ an approach which also sensitizes the obtained spectra to changes triggered by electrode polarization. Such an approach is based on a subtraction of the O K-edge spectrum corresponding to the initial state of the electrode, i.e. in our case to the lowest potential at the beginning of each cyclic polarization experiment. This converts the raw spectra into difference spectra reflecting only the changes triggered by polarization (see Fig. 3b). Presented difference spectra may contain two types of signals - positive (i.e. pointing towards more positive values of $\Delta\mu$) and negative (pointing towards more negative values of $\Delta\mu$). These peaks can be in the first approximation assigned to changes in population of surface confined oxygen containing species. While the positive peaks can be associated with a formation and accumulation of oxygen containing species absent at the reference potential, the negative peaks may indicate a consumption of oxygen containing species, originally present in the system (either in the interface or in the electrode) in electrochemical or chemical corrosion of the electrode. The difference spectra reflecting

Fig. 3. O K-edge XANES spectra recorded on RuO₂ electrode polarized between 0.70 and 1.87 V in 0.1 M HClO₄ at a polarization rate of 5 mV/s (left) and difference spectrum ($\Delta\mu = \mu_{1.87V} - \mu_{0.77V}$) reflecting changes in the absorption between the state of the electrode at 1.87 and 0.77 V vs. RHE.

the changes in the oxygen absorption during cyclic polarization of Ru and RuO₂ electrodes are shown as contour plots in Figs. 4(a) and (b), respectively. As one can expect, one observes a clear potential related absorption changes at energies characteristic for oxygen and intermediates of its electrocatalytic evolution. In addition to the changes of the absorption one may reasonably expect for oxygen evolution we observe also a potential controlled change of absorption at 534 eV characteristic for water bound oxygen (see Fig. 4a) and at 533 eV (see Fig. 4b). It needs to be noted that namely the last signal bears apparently no relevance to the theoretically predicted absorption of OER intermediates.

Although the contour plots presented in Fig. 4 provide an information describing all the absorption changes in the system, their practical use to reflect changes triggered by anodic oxygen evolution may be cumbersome.

To focus the analysis on the changes connected with OER we will in detail analyze potential dependent change of absorption at energies related to the OER, i.e., at energies characteristic for absorption of oxygen (at 531 eV) and of the theory predicted OER intermediates [16] -OH, -O and -OOH intermediates, which were reported to absorb (depending whether being in *cus* and *bridge* position) at 528.6, 529.1 and 531 eV, respectively [29]. Complete difference spectra for the individual energies of OER intermediates are shown in the Supporting information in Figure S1.

Detailed analysis of the electrocatalytic behavior of Ru and RuO₂ based electrodes will be given for each type of the electrocatalyst separately. Although the analysis of the behavior of Ru electrodes may be of high interest due to their higher anodic activity (see Fig. 2), the interpretation of the spectral behavior is rather complicated by the intrinsic instability of Ru electrodes at the potentials close to oxygen evolution. In this context, the less active, but more stable RuO₂ based system is more convenient to establish fundamental rules needed for interpretation of the differential O K-edge X-ray absorption spectra recorded under OER evolution conditions in acid media.

3.3. Ruthenium dioxide electrode

Detailed analysis of the contour plots, summarizing the change of oxygen related absorption in polarized RuO₂ electrolyte interphase under OER evolution conditions (Fig. 4(b)), identifies a main spectral region with pronounced change in the absorption coefficient located near 531 eV. Closer inspection, however, also finds less pronounced

changes of absorption at 533 eV and 529 eV. Potential dependence of the $\Delta\mu$ at each of these energies is shown in Fig. 5.

The signal at 531 eV, despite being the strongest, has restricted analytic value due to a lack of its specificity integrating contributions from the absorption of surface confined -OOH as well as from molecular oxygen [29,33]. It needs to be noted that the main change of $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV is observed at potentials where one observes exponential increase of the anodic current, suggesting that the formation of gaseous oxygen may be primary contributor to this signal. It also shows relatively small hysteresis (i.e. difference between anodic and cathodic branches of $\Delta\mu$ vs. electrode potential curve), which attests to an electrochemical nature of the underlying processes (see Fig. 5(a)). Although the main part of the $\Delta\mu$ increase at 531 eV is recorded at rather positive potentials its actual onset is observed ca. 200 mV negative to the onset of the exponential increase of the current. This suggests that an accumulation of OOH confined species at the surface dominates at these conditions. This behavior suggests that despite the high stability of thermally grown RuO₂, there is a change in the surface composition prior to the oxygen evolution process and this change in the surface composition can be attributed mainly to the accumulation of OOH species in the interface.

This reflects the fact that the potential dependence of the absorption at 529 eV which may be taken as spectral fingerprint of surface confined OH and O intermediates (region around 529 eV - see Fig. 5b) is rather small (see Fig. 5(b)). The signal of the surface confined OH /O groups shows relatively small change in the potential range 1.40 –1.70 V vs RHE which is followed by a small decrease at potentials above 1.70 V. The signal at 529 eV shows a small hysteric loop at potentials close to the vertex potential (1.98 V vs RHE) before it starts to track the anodic branch of the $\Delta\mu$ vs. E curve during the cathodic scan. It is also worth mentioning that a change of the absorption at 529 eV for IrO_x based electrodes was attributed to a formation of highly reactive oxyl-like groups in *cus* position [35,36,37]. These oxyl-like groups are then perceived as the needed precursors for the oxygen evolution process but their actual surface concentration does not exceed a fraction of a monolayer [38].

The signal of the $\Delta\mu$ at 533 eV (see Fig. 5(c)), on the other hand, shows practically no change before its sharp decrease at potentials positive to 1.55 V vs RHE. The observed decrease of the signal at 533 eV coincides with the onset of the exponential anodic current increase. A small hysteresis can be observed at potentials close to 1.80 V before the signal recorded during cathodic scan starts to track that observed during anodic polarization. The observed absorption change at 533 eV is

Fig. 4. 2D contour maps showing the progression of O K-edge spectra of (a) Ru electrode and (b) RuO₂ electrode during cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO₄ at 5 mV/s. The map summarizes the development of the populations of oxygen containing species at the Ru surface during first 5 cycles. In the case of RuO₂ it summarizes the behavior observed during 3 subsequent cycles. The left pane shows in both figures shows the applied potential perturbation. The color scheme then represents the absorption coefficient as a function of the electrode potential.

relatively difficult to qualify. First of all, this characteristic energy does not match any theoretically predicted OER intermediate nor bulk oxygen present in the structure of RuO₂. Although the observed potential driven change in the absorption coefficient at 533 eV cannot be straightforwardly attributed to a change of an OER intermediate population, it can be still rationalized reflecting the nature of O K-edge spectra – namely their ability to reflect the local electronic structure around Ru [32].

As outlined above, the characteristic O K-edge spectra reflect not only the initial electronic state of material but also its end state when the excited electron remains confined to the electronic structure of the

absorbing material. This fact allows to alter the interpretation of negative going signals in the differential spectra since these do not need to reflect a decrease in the number of oxygen containing species (a change in the population of the initial states) but may reflect also a decrease in the availability of the final states (i.e. change in the local electron density around Ru). In this context one may resolve the problematic assignment of the negative signal at 533 eV in the OER potential range assuming that this signal is caused by a change of the local electron density on Ru which is caused by actual oxygen evolution process (see coincidence of the decrease in the absorption at 533 eV with the onset of exponential current increase).

Fig. 5. Variation of the absorption coefficient $\Delta\mu$ at (a) 531 eV, (b) 529 eV, (c) 533 eV as a function of the electrode potential during cyclic polarization of the thermally grown RuO_2 electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 at 5 mV/s. The arrows mark the direction of the polarization.

Given the fact that the presented X-ray absorption spectra were recorded at conditions when the whole OER catalytic cycle (see Eqs. (1)–(4)) progresses, one has to expect that the electronic structure of the catalysts will significantly differ from that anticipated in the theoretical models addressing, e.g. adsorption energies of the key OER intermediates [16]. One needs to reflect the fact that the catalyst under reaction conditions aids the transfer of the electrons originally located in water molecules into an external circuit. This additional electron density is to be expected for all electrocatalytic oxidations and in the case of metal oxides it may be localized into specific states in the d-band reflecting directionality of the binding of the intermediates at the active sites distinguishing effectively between active and spectator sites at the surface.

In the particular case of the oxygen evolution, we may formally assume that this additional (and temporary) electron density may be attributed to a change in population of surface sites at the reaction conditions. This formalism would attribute this additional electron density, to a relative increase of the surface oxygen vacancies, which enter the catalytic cycle as the reactant in the first electron transfer step (see Eq. (1)). The steady state population of these vacant sites under OER conditions may significantly differ from that at less positive potentials.

This additional electron density remains localized in the d-band in the energy states involved in binding the OER intermediates i.e. in states formed by hybridization $\text{O } 2p^*$ antibonding orbitals with $\text{Ru } 3d e_g$ orbitals. This increase in electron density decreases probability of the excitation $\text{O } 1s$ electrons of “bulk” oxygen into $\text{Ru } 3d e_g$ related energy levels causing a decrease of the absorption at 533 eV. This behavior is rather counterintuitive given the expected d^4 configuration of tetravalent ruthenium which suggests that any change in the electronic

structure should primarily affect $\text{Ru } 3d t_{2g}$ occupation. Observed behavior, on the other hand, agrees well with the theoretical analysis based on binding energy calculations, which predicts that the active intermediates in oxygen evolution process bind solely to the so called *cus* sites which preferentially employ orbitals contributing to e_g band in its binding (vide infra). [16,32]

3.3.1. Ru electrode

Metallic Ru is reported to be a highly active but poorly stable electrode material for the oxygen evolution reaction [39–41]. In line with the general expectation that gaseous oxygen only evolves on oxide-covered electrodes, one should anticipate that polarization of a Ru in acidic media leads to in situ formation of surface oxide(s) prior to the actual oxygen evolution. Both these processes (i.e. surface oxide deposition and oxygen evolution) should result in significant oxygen accumulation in the interphase, which should also be reflected in the O K-edge absorption spectra. The data summarized in Fig. 4(a) as well as in Fig. 6 indicate gradual accumulation of the oxygen containing species at the interface which is in line with predicted formation of surface oxide(s). This oxygen accumulation is triggered by anodic polarization and is, in part, reversibly controlled by the electrode potential. It should be emphasized that the electrocatalytic behavior of the partially oxidized Ru surface shows a pronounced dependence on the electrode history.

The oxidation (and subsequent oxygen evolution) of Ru surface causes a change in X-ray absorption in almost all regions predicted by DFT analysis for the OER intermediates and Ru based oxides. A characteristic change in the absorption is encountered at 529, 531, 533 and 534 eV (see Figs. 6(a)–(d)). It needs to be noted that the spectral behavior triggered by the surface changes associated with surface oxidation and

Fig. 6. Variation of the absorption coefficient $\Delta\mu$ at (a) 534 eV, (b) 531 eV, (c) 529 eV and (d) 533 eV as a function of the electrode potential during first (black) and fourth (blue) cycle of cyclic polarization of the vapor-deposited Ru electrode in 0.1 M HClO₄ at 5 mV/s. The arrows mark the direction of the polarization.

oxygen evolution namely at 529 and 534 eV is more significant than for the thermally grown oxide, moreover, they show a pronounced development during repetitive cycling. Such a behavior is not observed on RuO₂ based electrodes. The overall trend caused by cycling is presented on a comparison of two cycles (first and fourth) in Fig. 6.

To distinguish between the surface oxide growth process and the oxygen evolution intermediate build-up, it is necessary to follow the reversibility of the observed spectral signal with respect to the electrode polarization. It can be expected that surface oxide growth should be irreversible (i.e., the surface oxide-related signal increases in the anodic scan and remains constant in the cathodic scan), whereas the reversible (with respect to potential) increase in oxygen-related absorption during the anodic polarization can be expected for OER intermediates and gaseous oxygen.

While the signals located at 529, 533 and 534 eV show initially an irreversible behavior, the signal located at 531 eV retains significant reversibility even in the first cycle. It needs to be noted that only the signal located at 534 eV attributable to water related oxygen remains mainly irreversible in all cycles (see Fig. 6a). The apparent uptake of the water shown in the spectra at 534 eV is triggered in the anodic scan by the electrode exposure to potentials positive to 1.2 V in the 1st cycle or 1.50 V in the 4th cycle. The significant uptake of the water is compliant with the fact that natively grown oxide should be of hydrous nature. It should be emphasized that the oxygen X-ray absorption spectra of the hydrous oxide formed on oxidized Ru electrode do not show any tendency to dissolution during cycling in the given potential range. The observed behavior may be misinterpreted as apparently conflicting the

known low stability of vapor-deposited Ru electrodes [39–41]. In fact the observed spectral behavior rather suggests that the actual hydrous ruthenium oxide may be relatively more stable at the experimental conditions compared with other oxygen containing species which are not stabilized by water molecules.

The signals attributable to oxygen and OER intermediates (located at 529, 531 eV) show a different behavior which changes from irreversible into a reversible one in subsequent cycles. The signals located at 531 and 529 eV (see Figs. 6b and c, respectively) may be attributed to molecular oxygen and surface confined peroxy species (531 eV) and to surface confined OH and O species (529 eV), respectively. The potential courses of both these signals are, however, rather complex to support the assignment of these signals solely to OER intermediates or oxygen. The accumulation of all these oxygen containing species is observed at fairly negative potentials (ca 0.9 V vs. RHE), which is well below the oxygen evolution range. One, therefore, has to assume that an increase of absorption at these energies reflects also a formation of a surface oxide structure(s).

Rationalization of the signal at 531 eV (Fig. 6b) can be based on assumption that the signal reflects a surface oxide formation along with actual molecular oxygen evolution. Possible contributions of different intermediates/products to the measured signal at 531 eV can be elucidated from the first derivative of the measured difference spectrum (see Figure S2). The spectroscopic signal at 531 eV starts to increase at about 0.9 V vs. RHE and reaches a linear increase with potential above 1.2 V vs. RHE (see Fig. S2). The $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV then shows an exponential increase with potential, at potentials positive to 1.47 V vs. RHE, which is

consistent with assumed evolution of the molecular oxygen. An analogous spectral behavior is also observed during cathodic scan when the oxygen evolution is not observed at potentials below 1.17 V (see Figure S2).

Slightly different behavior is observed for the signal located at 529 eV which may be attributed to surface confined OH/O groups (see Fig. 6c), which keeps increasing during the entire anodic scan suggesting no chemical or mechanical instability. More detailed information on the origin of this signal can be extracted from its derivative (see Figure S2 (b)). The time derivative of the signal at 529 eV clearly shows that the nature of the processes supporting the absorption at 529 eV changes with electrode history. A formation of irreversibly deposited surface oxides dominates on fresh electrodes (i.e. in the first cycle), but changes into a more complex behavior with progressive cycling when the formation of OER intermediate species becomes evident at potentials positive to 1.45 V vs. RHE (see Figure S2c) when the onset of actual oxygen evolution causes a decrease in the derivative of this signal which could be reflecting a decrease of OER intermediate population.

More complex behavior is observed for the absorption at 533 eV, which shows pronounced change during the electrode cycling. The most characteristic feature which remains independent of the cycling is the electrode potential driven decrease of the absorption at potentials positive to 1.4 V vs RHE which coincides with the actual oxygen evolution (see Fig. 2a). As in the case of thermally grown RuO₂ this absorption signal corresponds to a temporary redistribution of the electron density in the d-band due to the transfer of electrons from water to the external circuit. The interpretation of the absorption at 533 eV observed outside of the OER interval is rather difficult on the Ru based electrodes. In the first cycle one observes a pronounced increase of the absorption at this energy namely during cathodic scan. A similar, although more, reversible behavior of the absorption coefficient is observed at the electrode in the subsequent cycles. It needs to be born in mind that the absorption at 533 eV is characteristic for Ru oxides and namely for development of their d-band structure. The increase of the absorption observed outside of the OER potential interval, therefore can be attributed to a formation of surface oxides and development of the band structure during cycling.

It should be emphasized that the interpretation of XAS data observed on Ru electrodes is significantly more difficult than that of the RuO₂ electrodes. This fact can be attributed to a smaller adherence of the surface structures formed at the Ru electrode surface under *reaction conditions* to the structures involved in the theoretical models as well as to a low stability of Ru based electrodes leading to continuous formation/dissolution of the surface oxide layers.

3.4. OER mechanism

Above outlined reaction mechanism describes the OER as a sequence of four individual electron/proton transfer steps (1) –(4). One can, therefore, expect a presence of four types of surface species related to the OER: i) surface confined OH species (OER intermediates resulting from the first electron transfer reaction), ii) surface confined oxo species (OER intermediates formed in the second electron transfer step), iii) surface confined peroxy species (OER intermediate of the third electron transfer step) and iv) vacant surface sites entering the whole catalytic cycle. The OER process proceeds as a sequence and can be kinetically controlled by the slowest reaction step. This kinetic control should be observable in the XAS spectra, which in such a case should reflect an accumulation of the OER intermediate entering the rate limiting step. This specific accumulation, therefore, can be used to identify the rate limiting step.

Kinetic control by the second electron transfer in the OER reaction sequence should result in accumulation of surface confined OH (absorbing at 529 eV) [29] in the interphase. Analogously, kinetic control by the third electron transfer should lead to an accumulation of surface confined O (absorbing at 529.5 eV) [29]. The observed accumulation of the OOH at the surface deviates from both predictions and suggests kinetic control of the whole process by the fourth electron

transfer step. However, this spectroscopic indication of the rate determining step should be taken with care as there is a notable slowing of the increase of the absorption coefficient at 531 eV at the most positive potentials indicating gradual removal of the surface confined OOH. Such a trend is compatible with kinetic control by the third electron transfer at high overpotentials which is theoretically predicted.

The analysis of O K-edge XAS spectra taken under OER conditions on the native oxides grown *in-situ* at the Ru surface does not allow to identify the rate limiting step. There is a simultaneous (and qualitatively almost identical) increase of the absorption for all theoretically conceived OER intermediates. This behavior does not allow to determine the rate limiting step, which can be ascribed to the complexity of the natively grown oxides in which it is rather difficult to distinguish between species actually involved in oxygen evolution and spectators.

A special role in the analysis of OER plays the absorption at 533 eV the variation of which we attribute to OER related changes of the local electronic structure. It needs to be noted that although this absorption signal is not related to binding of OER intermediates it still keeps high relevance to the characterization of the catalyst / electrode interface and can be used for indirect identification of the active sites. The absorption at 533 eV reflects occupation of Ru 3d e_g related energy states in the conduction band which are primarily used to channel the electrons from water into external circuit. Specific involvement of the Ru 3d e_g orbitals conforms to theoretical prediction of the OER active sites made by DFT calculation [16]. The observed behavior in fact just accentuates the importance of engineering band structure in advanced OER catalyst design [42]

4. Conclusions

The X-ray absorption experiments following the types and populations of oxygen-containing species at the surface of Ru and Ru oxide based electrodes in acids under OER conditions, confirm that the actual oxygen evolution proceeds exclusively on oxide covered surface. They also show that the actual oxygen evolution processes may be controlled by a different elementary step depending on the applied electrode potential. The oxygen evolution on thermally grown RuO₂, which is expected to have a surface structure and composition close to that of thermodynamically stable rutile-type oxide, is kinetically controlled by removal of the fourth electron at potentials negative to 1.7 V vs. RHE. This kinetic control seems to be removed at more positive potentials. The fact that the bulk oxygen evolution is accompanied with a decrease of absorption at 533 eV is compliant with the expected transfer of the electrons from water to the external circuit which affects the distribution of electron density around transition metal (Ru). This electron transfer is confined to orbitals contributing to 3d e_g orbital of Ru. This behavior is in agreement with the theoretical prediction of the OER being confined to *cus* positions [16].

The metal Ru-based electrode needs to form a surface oxide prior to the actual oxygen evolution and appears to be more active than the thermodynamically stable oxide. This enhanced activity is difficult to rationalize given the accumulation of the oxygen containing species in the *in-situ* formed hydrous surface oxides. Despite the uncertainty caused by the surface oxide buildup the actual OER is again characterized by a decrease of the absorption at 533 eV suggesting that also in the case of hydrous oxide is confined to *cus* reaction sites.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kaoruho Sakata: Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Kateřina Mínhová Macounová:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Kenta Amemiya:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Petr Krtil:** Writing – original draft, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

None of the authors declares any competing interests.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

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